

Awareness of Leprosy in Patients Attending Dermatology OPD of Tertiary Care Centre in Eastern Bihar

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Abstract:

Background: Although various measures are taken to create awareness about the epidemiological features of leprosy and encourage health-seeking behavior, they have seldom been able to tackle the high incidence of new leprosy cases in India. This paper discusses the current awareness of leprosy among diagnosed leprosy patients attending Dermatology OPD of tertiary care centre in Eastern Bihar.

Methodology: This research work was a cross-sectional hospital-based study conducted in the Department of Dermatology Venereology and leprosy (DVL) at Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College and Lions Seva Kendra Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar. This study was done in accordance with the Helsinki declaration (2000) and carried out after obtaining the Institutional Ethics Committee clearance. The clinical and epidemiological data was obtained based on a pre-designed proforma which included demographic details, duration of illness, and treatment status of the patient. Awareness regarding the disease and disabilities were evaluated by set of questionnaire which included the knowledge about the disease, disabilities and treatment.

Results: Out of 76 patients 85.5% of respondents had heard about leprosy. Various beliefs were cited, with 32.9% attributing it to a curse by God, 28.9% to hereditary causes, and smaller percentages to punishment for family sins, unclean endearment, and bacterial causes. Skin patches were the most recognized symptom (55.3%), followed by skin irritation (46.0%) and loss of sensation (42.1%). Casual contact was the most commonly mentioned mode (42.1%), followed by aerosol droplets (28.9%), and other less frequent modes. About 82.9% believed leprosy is curable. About 60.5 % patients had answer pharmaceutical drugs is the treatment of leprosy.

Conclusion: The present study shows a lack of awareness and knowledge of leprosy among the target population. This study sheds light on the significant burden of disabilities associated with leprosy and underscores the importance of continued efforts in education, early detection, and effective treatment to reduce the impact of this disease on affected individuals and communities.

Keywords: Leprosy, awareness, Eastern India, Bihar, Demography.

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Introduction

Leprosy is one of the oldest diseases of mankind and yet persists as a public health problem in many parts of the world. It is an infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae* and primarily affects the skin and peripheral nerves [1]. The mode of transmission is believed to occur through droplet spread or prolonged skin contact with an untreated leprosy

patient. Patients with leprosy who present at later stages of the disease usually develop irreversible disabilities and disfigurement [2]. Physical deformities in addition to socio-cultural misconceptions about leprosy have led to social stigma and discrimination of "People with Leprosy" (PWL) throughout history. Social stigma has been a major

factor contributing to delay in seeking treatment by leprosy patients. This has been a significant obstacle to early detection, prompt treatment, and cure of leprosy patients [3, 4].

Leprosy is endemic in several states and union territories of India, with the annual case detection rate of 4.56 per 10 000 population. The prevalence rate of leprosy is 0.4 per 10,000 population in the country. Of the new cases detected during 2020-2021, 58.1% were multibacillary, 39% were women, 5.8% were children less than 14 years of age, and 2.41% had visible deformities. The rate of visible deformities was 1.1 per million population [5].

Despite success of the NLEP, India has the highest burden of the disease. India, along with Brazil, Indonesia accounted for 79.6% of all the new cases detected globally in 2018 and is among the 22 “global priority countries” that contribute 95% of the world numbers of leprosy, warranting a sustained effort to bring the numbers down. Of the total new cases detected, almost 50% were multibacillary (MB) leprosy, and the number of pediatric cases continues to remain high, both indicating continued transmission of leprosy in the community [6]. There are pockets of high endemicity in the country along with many undetected cases in the community because of low voluntary reporting due to lack of awareness, as well as the fear, stigma, misconceptions, and discrimination which continue to grow in the society. Hence, the challenges remain with the continued delay in detecting new patients, and therefore, increasing the number of people with deformities, high new case detection rates, high prevalence of childhood leprosy, and persisting discrimination against people affected with leprosy [7-10].

The patients with a frequency of disability in WHO grade 2 disability rate has often been used as an indicator for the magnitude of the morbidity due to leprosy in the community whereas early detection and management of patients with WHO grade 1 disability (G1D) is more important for the prevention of development of deformities among leprosy patients [11]. In Eastern Bihar, where leprosy prevalence remains high, understanding the clinical-epidemiological profile of disability in leprosy is crucial for informing targeted interventions and optimizing disease management strategies. Despite the availability of multidrug therapy (MDT) and other treatment modalities, challenges persist in

early diagnosis, access to care, and addressing socio-cultural barriers that hinder disease control efforts [12].

This study aimed to detect the awareness of leprosy among the leprosy patients and fill existing knowledge gaps among patients attending Dermatology OPD of a tertiary care center in Eastern Bihar. Inappropriate knowledge and erroneous beliefs about leprosy and the disabilities caused by the disease are the main reasons for the stigma attached to the disease. The current research was embarked to determine the knowledge and attitude of the leprosy patients attending Department of Dermatology Venerology and leprosy (DVL) OPD towards leprosy.

Materials & Methods

This research work was a cross-sectional hospital-based study conducted in the Department of Dermatology Venerology and Leprosy (DVL) at Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College and Lions Seva Kendra Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar. The study was undertaken as a part of thesis protocol submitted to the university. This study was done in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration (2000) and carried out after obtaining the Institutional Ethics Committee clearance. Duration of Study was between 1st September 2022 to 30th April 2024. All patients presenting with cardinal signs of leprosy and willing to participate in the study through a written informed consent were included in the study. We have used questionnaire which had been validated in Hindi and English as the tool for assessing the awareness in patients with leprosy.

The clinical and epidemiological data was obtained based on a pre-designed proforma which included demographic details, duration of illness, and treatment status of the patient. Awareness regarding the disease and disabilities were evaluated by set of questionnaire which included the knowledge about the disease, disabilities and treatment. This is a questionnaire-based descriptive study. All clinical data were recorded at first visit. In the analysis of results, the data collected will be entered in Microsoft Excel Sheet, and analysis to be conducted by using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software (IBM, California, USA) version 20.0. A value $p \leq 0.05$ at 95% confidence intervals was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Demographic information of study participants

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
18-30 years	29	38.2
31-40 years	17	22.4
41-50 years	13	17.1
51-60 years	11	14.5
61-70 years	4	5.3

>70 years	2	2.6
Mean Age	38.34 ±14.67	
Sex		
Male	45	59.2
Female	31	40.8
Male: Female Ratio	1.45:1	
Residence		
Urban	8	10.5
Rural	68	89.5
Family History of Leprosy		
Yes	42	55.3
No	34	44.7
Socio-economic Status		
Upper (I)	2	2.6
Upper middle (II)	3	3.9
Lower middle (III)	15	19.7
Upper lower (IV)	26	34.2
Lower (V)	30	39.5
Total	76	100

In the present study a total of 76 leprosy patients were selected after meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Out of 76 patients majority of them were aged from 18-30 years (38.2%) followed by 31-40 years (22.4%), 41-50 years (14.5%), 61-70 years (5.3%) and >70 years (2.6%) with a mean age of 38.34 ±14.67 years. Out of 76 leprosy patients 45 (59.2%) were males and 31 (40.8%) were females with a male & female ratio was 1.45:1. Out of 76 patients enrolled in the present study 8 (10.5%) were from urban areas and 68 (89.5%) were from rural areas. In the present study 42 (55.3%) of the patients had positive family history of leprosy. Regarding socio-economic status (Kuppuswamy's Scale updated for 2020) of the study subjects we found majority of them were from lower class (39.5%) followed by upper lower (34.2%) and lower middle class (19.7%) [Table 1/ Fig. 1].

Figure 1: Socio-economic status (Kuppuswamy's Scale updated for 2020)

Table 2: Duration of leprosy and treatment status among participants

Duration of Disease	Frequency	Percentage
<6 months	7	9.2
6-12 months	50	65.8
13-24 months	16	21.1
25-36 months	3	3.9
Mean ±SD	12.25 ±6.30	
Treatment Status		

New cases /starting	57	75
Treatment of leprosy during the study period		
Partially Treated	3	3.9
Completely Treated	16	21.1

In the present study duration of the disease was maximum between 6 and 12 months found among 50 (65.8%) patients followed by 13 a mean duration of 12.25 ±6.30 months. In the present study out of total 76 leprosy patients, 57 (75%)

were new cases/starting treatment of leprosy during the study period, 3 (3.9%) were partially treated, and 16 (21.1%) had completed their treatment [Table 2].

Figure 2: Clinical spectrum of leprosy among study participants

Regarding the spectrum of leprosy according to the Ridley–Jopling classification we found that borderline tuberculoid (BT) leprosy was the most common (46.1%) followed by borderline lepromatous (BL) leprosy (30.3%), lepromatous (LL) leprosy (19.7%) and pure neuritic leprosy (3.9%) [Fig. 2].

Table 3: WHO clinical type of leprosy among study participants

WHO clinical type of Leprosy	Frequency	Percentage
PB	25	32.9
MB	51	67.1
Total	76	100

Above analysis the distribution of the patients according to NLEP classification, 51 (67.1%) of them were found to have multibacillary (MB) type of leprosy, whereas only 25 (32.9%) had paucibacillary (PB) type [Table 3].

Table 4: Awareness among the leprosy among study participants

Knowledge related questions	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Have you heard about leprosy?	Yes	65	85.5
	No	11	14.5
What causes leprosy?	Punishment for sin of family	11	14.5
	Due to curse by God	25	32.9
	Hereditary causes	22	28.9
	Unclean endearment cause	10	13.2
	Bacterial Cause	8	10.5
What is /are symptom of leprosy?	It causes skin irritation	35	46
	It can present at skin patches	42	55.3
	Loss of sensation	32	42.1
	It can led to deformities or disal	9	11.8
	Aerosol droplets	22	28.9

What is are means leprosy transmission?	Casual Contact	32	42.1
	Contaminated water	5	6.6
	Sexual contact	6	7.9
	Prolonged contact	1	1.3
	Site beside patients	1	1.3
	Share items with patients	0	0
Is leprosy cured?	Yes	63	82.9
	No	13	17.1
What is/are the treatment of leprosy?	Pharmaceutical Drugs	46	60.5
	Traditional mode of treatment	10	13.1
	Religious ritual treatment	9	11.8
	I do not know	11	14.5

Out of 76 patients 85.5% of respondents had heard about leprosy. Various beliefs were cited, with 32.9% attributing it to a curse by God, 28.9% to hereditary causes, and smaller percentages to punishment for family sins, unclean endearment, and bacterial causes. Skin patches were the most recognized symptom (55.3%), followed by skin irritation (46.0%) and loss of sensation (42.1%). Casual contact was the most commonly mentioned mode (42.1%), followed by aerosol droplets (28.9%), and other less frequent modes. 82.9% believed leprosy is curable. About 60.5 % patients had answer pharmaceutical drugs is the treatment of leprosy.

Discussion

In current years under leprosy control program more attention has been given to prevention of disability. Current focus of health authorities and governments across the globe is on tackling stigma due to Leprosy. One of the major factors responsible for stigmatization of leprosy patients is their identification in society due to visible deformities. In the present study out of 300 leprosy patients 76 had some kind of disabilities. Therefore the disability prevalence among leprosy patients in the present study was 25.3%. Out of 76 patients majority of them were aged from 18-30 years (38.2%) followed by 31-40 years (22.4%), 41-50 years (14.5%), 61-70 years (5.3%) and >70 years (2.6%) with a mean age of 38.34 ±14.67 years. In study conducted by Kar et al reported that 60% were aged above 40 years and 40% were in 21 to 40 years age group [17] Reddy et al reported in his study 30.76% were above 40years.[96] Anil Kumar et al in his study reported 65% of the patients in their study group belongs to age above 59 years [18] In Raghavendra et al study, peak age group affected was 21 to 30 years (20%) followed by 41 to 50 years (18%) and 61 to 70 years (18%). So, the data in current study is in accordance with data recorded in previous studies [19]. In a study conducted by Mohammad Adil et al, 47.1% of the patients were between 21-40 yrs of age and 14.2% were below 16 yrs, showing a comparatively younger age profile of the patients [20]. Agarwal et al in their study reported that 49% of the patients

belonged to the 41-60 yrs age group followed by those in the 21-40 yrs age group. Only 6% of the patients were less than 20 yrs of age [21]. Out of 76 leprosy patients 45 (59.2%) were males and 31 (40.8%) were females. In a hospital based retrospective study conducted by Peters ES between 1988 to 1997, it was reported that 66% of patients were males and 33% were females with a ratio of 2:1 [22]. In WHO expert committee report of 2003 on leprosy situation in India, 63.2% were males and 33.8% were females [23]. Raghavendra et al in their study reported, 78% were males and 22% were females. Male to female ratio was 3.5:1[19]. In a study conducted by Mohammad Adil et al, 67.6% of the patients were males and 32.4% were females, male: female ratio being 2.08:1 showing higher female patients in their study [20]. In yet another study conducted by Nigam et al, the male: female ratio is 2.6:1 [24]. Agarwal et al in their study reported 77% of the patients were males and 23% were females, the male: female ratio being 3.34, showing higher incidence of the disease among males [21]. In the present study 42 (55.3%) of the patients had positive family history of leprosy. But, in a study conducted by Nigam et al in 30.7% of the patients there was a positive family history [24]. In a study conducted by Patil et al, 25% of the patients gave positive contact history, with majority of them being a positive family member.[104] Regarding socio-economic status of the study subjects we found majority of them were from lower class (39.5%) followed by upper lower (34.2%) and lower middle class (19.7%). Raghavendra et al in their study reported that, 56% patients belonged to lower class, 42% belonged to middle class and 2% belonged to upper class.[98] Regarding the spectrum of leprosy according to the Ridley-Jopling classification we found that borderline tuberculoid (BT) leprosy was the most common (46.1%) followed by borderline lepromatous (BL) leprosy (30.3%), lepromatous (LL) leprosy (19.7%) and pure neuritic leprosy (3.9%) [19]. Gopalakrishnan S et al study (2021) had revealed that among the study participants, 54.7% of the participants had adequate knowledge and 23.3% had favourable attitude towards leprosy. With regard to knowledge, 66% of the participants

believe that leprosy is a serious disease, and 71.2% of them were aware of transmission of leprosy from person to person. With regard to attitude, 57.7% were afraid of being diagnosed with leprosy, and 57% felt compassion and desire to help those diagnosed with leprosy. With regard to health-seeking behaviour, around 83% preferred treatment from government hospitals and allopathic treatment. Male sex, occupation, education, and marital status were found to be having statistically significant association with knowledge, while the latter two were found to be associated with favourable attitude towards leprosy. Unfavourable attitude and inadequate knowledge regarding leprosy was found among the study participants. Behaviour change communication programs have to be enhanced at community level to improve the knowledge and attitude regarding leprosy among the population [13].

In Reddy NV et al study (2022) [10] a total 400 participants were studied, out of which 205 (51.25%) were females and 195 (48.75%) were males. Only 154/400 (38.5%) people were aware of leprosy. 130/400 (32.5%) people thought that it is treatable; however, 71/130 (54.6) of them thought that it would recur even after completing the treatment. Only 103/400 (25.75) said that they would marry a person with leprosy, denoting prevalent stigma in the society, and 79/400 (19.75) were aware of government services for leprosy and NLEP. Screening of all the participants surveyed did not reveal any new or doubtful cases of leprosy. The present study shows a lack of awareness and knowledge of leprosy among the target population. With only 20% of them being aware of government services and the NLEP, combined with an extremely low knowledge about the disease; it shows the need to further augment the government programs. There is also an increasing need to educate people to accomplish a positive attitude of the community towards leprosy patients. A similar finding was reported by a study conducted by Raju MS et al., where 35%–50% of the participants were noted to have adequate knowledge on leprosy, but the attitude was more in negative [14]. A study conducted by Mohite RV et al. in a rural community in Karad reported that nearly 79% of respondents had good knowledge and 69% had a positive attitude towards leprosy [15]. Singh R et al. in a community-based study in Nepal noted that only 42% of the study population had good knowledge and a favourable attitude on leprosy [16]. This shows that the knowledge and attitude of the population towards leprosy is still low despite the disease being eliminated from the country. The Government of India has launched National Strategic Plan (NSP) & Roadmap for Leprosy (2023-27) on 30th January, 2023, to achieve zero transmission of leprosy by 2027 i.e. three years ahead of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG)

3.3. The NSP and Roadmap contains implementation strategies, year-wise targets, public health approaches and overall technical guidance for the programme. The strategy and roadmap focuses on awareness for zero stigma & discrimination, promotion of early case detection, prevention of disease transmission by prophylaxis (Leprosy Post Exposure Prophylaxis) and roll out of web-based information portal (Nikusth 2.0) for reporting of leprosy cases [17].

The Nigam P et al study(1977) was carried out in the three villages viz. Kochha Bhanwar, Kargawan and Pichhore, situated within 3 kms radius from M.L.B. Medical College, Jhansi, U.P. About 91 per cent (91.17%) of population was surveyed. Out of the 3,362 individuals studied, 18 cases of leprosy could be detected giving a prevalence rate of 5.41/1000 population. The highest prevalence rate (7.40/1000) was seen in age group 15-49 years with male to female ratio of 2.6: 1. The disease was not prevalent in preschool age-group. Poor class of people contributed comparatively to a greater extent (6.37/1000). Size of the family did also not seem to be associated with the prevalence of disease. More than one case of leprosy in a family was observed in 30.7 per cent of the families. Early cases of leprosy remained acceptable in rural society whereas advanced cases were not acceptable. The disease seemed to manifest at all ages except pre-school age group. Majority of the cases (55.56%) were of early stage with a duration of the disease of less than 2 years. Possibilities to arrest the disease by early diagnosis, and prompt and proper treatment have been emphasized [26].

Conclusion

The present study shows a lack of awareness and knowledge of leprosy among the target population. Interestingly, despite a high level of awareness about leprosy among respondents, there were misconceptions about its causes, with some attributing it to divine curse or hereditary factors. However, the majority believed that leprosy is curable, with pharmaceutical drugs being the preferred treatment choice. This study sheds light on the significant burden of disabilities associated with leprosy and underscores the importance of continued efforts in education, early detection, and effective treatment to reduce the impact of this disease on affected individuals and communities.

Ethical approval

Ethics approval has been taken from IEC, Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College & L.S.K. Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar.

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